

IRREVERSIBILITY IN NATURE

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Typing on a computer display a program for calculating some phenomenon, if it is compiled correctly, one often finds oneself under hypnosis of dominance both over the machine and over the phenomenon that one perceives. The operator has the power to return to any previous step of the program, repeat any period in the cycle, the program is invertible, reversible. The past in real life, if it can be returned, then, alas, only in memory. It would seem that static works of art are extremely difficult to restore if they are damaged, it is almost impossible to restore to them that elusive, alive, but fragile, which is characteristic of creative work in general. You can also turn to simpler and more illustrative phenomena that demonstrate the property of irreversibility in time. Having broken a triangle of billiard balls with a cue, it is impossible to return to it in the game. The initially inflated wheel chamber will fall off in the event of a puncture and will not inflate by itself. A broken crystal vase cannot be collected... All this is so familiar that it would seem embarrassing to ask the question - why? No, in physics such a question in relation to phenomena in nature turned out to be by no means childish. Firstly, this question, or rather, reflection on the answer to it, made it possible to comprehend and understand the deepest layers that form the basis of physical phenomena. Secondly, both in laboratory and natural phenomena, there are phenomena in which something opposite is observed to what we get used to in the case of irreversibility. This is the so-called self-organization, when out of chaos, as if by itself, something rational is "created". The laser beam does not crumble if its intensity is high enough, the giant tsunami wave intensifies as it approaches the shore, as if being saturated with a small wave, the gold nugget "assembled" itself, finally, life in its development came from simple forms that showed the ability to self-assemble .

Irreversible processes occurring in isolated systems (or close to them) always lead to the growth of chaos states inside the systems. The measure of this chaos is entropy, which will be discussed below. The transition to chaos is accompanied by a steady increase in entropy over time, until the system comes to a state with the maximum possible entropy under given conditions. This state, which completes the degradation of

the system, is an equilibrium state. There is no turning back!

Regular processes in which something is created, unlike irreversible ones, are accompanied by a decrease in entropy. These processes are reversible, since systems can spontaneously or under the influence of an environment in thermal equilibrium (thermal reservoir or medium) go into a state of initial chaos. The computer that reads the program lowers its entropy. But at the same time, some part of the energy imparted to the machine is always used to heat it, the growth of chaotic fluctuations, which can lead to a failure in the operation of the machine. This applies to any mechanisms, machines, their systems. This is the requirement of the law of nature - the second law of thermodynamics. The product-determined chaos produced along with the useful is a tribute "paid" in accordance with the specified law. Such, for example, is the environmental tribute - pollution of the environment - which modern civilization pays to nature. It is impossible not to take this circumstance into account, otherwise the environmental tribute will turn into a boomerang that hurts and sometimes destroys the one who launched this boomerang.

It is unlikely that reversible and irreversible processes exist in pure form in nature. Such a division is conditional, and nature over the billions of years of its development has experienced the cataclysms of birth and destruction more than once, and each time after the destruction in one place, it had the strength to create a new one in another place and another time ...

And so the fatal inevitability, conditioned, in our terms, by the steady growth of entropy, leads to unexpected "twists of fate", as a result of which something new can be created. With free cooling of the gas, this process is spontaneous and is accompanied by a fatal increase in entropy, which will lead to lifeless individual random particles floating in space, i.e. to chaos, but if the gas is dense enough, which can be provided by attraction to some massive body, to a planet or a comet, then it may turn out that the cooling of such a gas will at some point turn it into a liquid due to the active action of exchange forces long-range order, which will lead to a jump in entropy and its decrease. Those. in the last example, the "unexpected" inclusion of the interaction prevented the fatality due to the laws of statistics.